

**glycan
trigger**

D5.2 - Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 2

WP5

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
CD	Crohn's disease
D&C&E	Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation
EER	Expected exploitable results
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HE	Horizon Europe
HCC	Healthcare community
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key Exploitation Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
R&D	Research and Development
TRL	Technology readiness level
WP	Work Package

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About the project

GlycanTrigger is a project funded by the European Union, within the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions (RIA). The long-term goal of GlycanTrigger is to unlock a new checkpoint that regulates health to chronic inflammation transition by proposing mucosa glycans modifications as a master switch towards the early perturbation of host-microbial interactions and the consequent activation of both innate and humoral immune systems. Ultimately, we want to intercept or revert this master switch and thereby exploit/analyse whether this constitutes an opportunity to prevent the development of chronic inflammation in at-risk individuals.

Chronic inflammation is the underlying cause of numerous diseases, including Crohn's disease (CD), which may have a preclinical phase with immunological changes occurring before symptoms manifest. To improve disease prediction and prevention, our innovative approach seeks to understand the health-to-intestinal inflammation transition using CD as a disease model. The GlycanTrigger project will investigate when, why and how changes in glycosylation at the surface of the gut mucosa, constitute an early trigger of the health-to-inflammation transition. We will address how changes in glycosylation of the gut mucosa act as a primary event that dysregulates not only local mechanisms, but also systemic mechanisms associated with health to inflammation transition. Although high-risk/high-gain, our project is based on appropriate and long-standing expertise and fundamental biological principles that the consortium has helped establish and is thus likely to lead to (i) breakthrough biomedical concepts in the driving factors that trigger the health to chronic inflammation transition and to (ii) novel predictive tools for early detection of at-risk individuals to develop chronic inflammation, as well as to (iii) a novel intervention strategy that will be tested for disease prevention. In the longer term, the results of GlycanTrigger will improve health literacy through better-informed management of health status, diet and life-style to maintain a healthy gut. Our strategy for understanding the transition from health to gut inflammation is comprehensive and includes the impact of mucosa glycans on local and systemic mechanisms.

Partners:

Number	Short Name	Legal Name
1	I3S (Coordinator)	I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO (Portugal)
2	LUMC	ACADEMISCH ZIEKENHUIS LEIDEN (The Netherlands)
3	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITÉ (France)
4	CHARITE	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETSMEDIZIN BERLIN (Germany)
5	GLSMED LH	GLSMED LEARNING HEALTH SA (Portugal)
5.1	HLL	HOSPITAL DA LUZ SA (Portugal)
6	MOUNT SINAI	ICAHN SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AT MOUNT SINAI (USA)
7	EFCCA	EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF CROHN'S AND ULCERATIVE COLITIS ASSOCIATIONS (Belgium)
8	SPI	SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACÃO CONSULTADORIA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTO DA INOVACÃO SA (Portugal)
9	LUD	LUDGER LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Executive Summary

The Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation (D&C&E) Plan 2 corresponds to Deliverable 5.2 of the GlycanTrigger project, which is developed under the framework of Work Package (WP) 5 “Dissemination, exploitation and communication”. SPI (Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação) is the main responsible for this deliverable and the implementation of the ongoing strategy, with the core contribution from i3S (Institute for Research and Innovation in Health), and EFCCA (European Federation of Crohn's and Ulcerative Colitis Associations).

This document is the second iteration of the strategic plan outlined for the GlycanTrigger under WP5. It builds upon the initial plan (D&C&E Plan 1, Deliverable 5.1), providing an update on the activities, strategies, and objectives for the effective dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the project's results. The updated plan improves the approach defined within the initial version, by incorporating lessons learned, new developments across the project and emerging opportunities to boost the project's visibility, impact, and engagement with stakeholders. It outlines the key tools, channels, and methodologies used to communicate the project's goals and achievements to both scientific and non-scientific audiences, in order to ensure a broader outreach and facilitate the exploitation of project outcomes.

This document also highlights the ongoing efforts to align with the project's overarching aims, in order to engage and empower the target groups through relevant dissemination actions and hosting of thematic events with special focus on health literacy and patient empowerment.

Through these actions, we guarantee that dissemination and exploitation activities continue to support the sustainability and long-term impact of the project's innovations, as well as contributing to the enrichment of collaborations with external stakeholders across sectors.

The GlycanTrigger D&C&E Plan outlines the outreach and engagement strategy, communication tools, materials, and partner activities, adapting as the project progresses to meet its evolving context and needs. The present deliverable will be further reviewed and updated in Deliverable D5.3, "Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation (D&C&E) Plan 3", which is due on December 31st, 2026.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

The present Deliverable 5.2, titled "Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation (D&C&E) Plan 2", constitutes an update to the existing strategy defined within the WP5 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication. It displays a comprehensive update into the initial D&C&E Plan, by detailing all actions performed thus far that reflects the progress and the evolution of the GlycanTrigger dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities.

WP5 has specific aims tailored to a set of major tasks that involves:

- i) Development and implementation of a robust dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy;
- ii) To establish a clear identity and branding for GlycanTrigger;
- iii) The mapping and engaging relevant stakeholders based on the needs and interests within the research field;
- iv) A strong integration of a patient-centred co-design approaches to boost a transformative change;
- v) To guarantee the exploitation of the project's outcomes to leave a lasting impact both in Europe and globally.

This deliverable not only discloses the D&C&E strategy but also highlights the tools, activities/campaigns, and channels employed to reinforce the visibility and outreach of GlycanTrigger. It serves as a guide for all partners in effectively disseminating and exploiting project results, ensuring a long-term impact beyond the project's duration. The actions outlined in this document reflect the current status of the project and will be continuously updated as the team gains further insight into target audiences and adjusts activities to address emerging gaps.

Through these strategies, GlycanTrigger aims to disseminate its progress effectively, raise awareness, and engage stakeholders throughout the project's lifecycle, ensuring that the project's messages and results reach their intended audiences.

Chapter 2

Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2. Communication and Dissemination Strategy

The GlycanTrigger project aims to advance knowledge on inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) by effectively communicating and disseminating its research findings and engaging stakeholders across Europe and beyond. The project communication and dissemination strategy developed in the first version of the D&C&E Plan outlines clear processes, responsibilities, and channels for ensuring the project's results and outcomes reach the right audiences and maximise impact. This strategy is collaboratively implemented across the project consortium, with each partner playing a critical role in reaching and engaging various stakeholders.

2.1 Communication Strategy

The GlycanTrigger communication strategy outlines the framework for communicating project outcomes and activities throughout the project's duration. The project key communication objectives includes: **(i)** engaging relevant stakeholders and partners early and consistently throughout the project lifecycle; **(ii)** avoiding a one-size-fits-all approach and instead tailoring communication to stakeholders' interests; **(iii)** adapting content and delivery methods to the target audience to ensure that key messages reach all potential beneficiaries, including through targeted translations; and **(iv)** frequently monitoring, evaluating (both internally and externally), and updating communication procedures based on GlycanTrigger's progress and outreach performance.

Currently, GlycanTrigger is in the third phase of implementing its communication strategy, focused on encouraging community engagement online and offline, with continuous updates based on performance reports (

Table 1). The first two phases focused on establishing the project's branding and communication framework, defining the project identity, setting communication objectives, mapping stakeholders, and introducing communication tools to raise awareness and enhance engagement.

Table 1 - GlycanTrigger Communication Strategy Implementation Phases

Phase 1 (M1 – M6)	Designing the communication strategy, defining project identity, establishing communication objectives, mapping stakeholders, and implementing initial channels (website and social media channels)
Phase 2 (M6 – M17)	Raising awareness through additional tools and channels (videos, e-newsletter, press release), refining the communication strategy, and adjusting based on feedback.
Phase 3 (M18 – M72)	Fostering community engagement through both online and offline channels, while continuously refining the communication strategy

The communication strategy continues to be guided by three main objectives defined in the first version of the D&C&E Plan, ensuring alignment with the overall goal of fostering engagement and visibility throughout the project lifecycle:

- **Project Visibility:** Raise awareness of the project's objectives and outcomes, ensuring the public and stakeholders understand the significance of the research on IBD.
- **Stakeholders Engagement:** Foster participation from a wide range of stakeholders, from healthcare professionals to patients and the public, ensuring their active involvement in project activities.
- **Educational Outreach:** Provide the public and healthcare professionals with up-to-date information about IBD and the project's progress on prevention, diagnosis, and treatment.

The communication strategy aims to deliver clear, consistent messaging tailored to different periods of the project, ensuring that the key outcomes are communicated effectively to the right audiences at the right time. These key messages are crafted to meet the evolving needs of stakeholders and adapt to the project's progress. In the initial phase of the project (M1-M24), the focus is on introducing GlycanTrigger, raising awareness of IBD, and establishing the foundational understanding of the project's goals and methodology.

Key Messages (M1-M24)

- **What is GlycanTrigger?** – Introduce the project and its mission to explore the role of glycans in IBD, and how its research can lead to new preventive and therapeutic strategies.
- **Raising Awareness on IBD** – Educate about IBD conditions (such as Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis) and their impact on patients' lives, emphasising the need for personalised prevention and treatment approaches.
- **Promotion of Health Literacy** – Support health literacy by providing clear, accessible information on how IBDs affect individuals and families, along with actionable strategies for managing health, diet, and lifestyle to maintain gut health and prevent disease onset.
- **Collaboration and Networking** – Foster collaboration among stakeholders (e.g., other (sister) EU-funded projects) to build a network of support.

As the project progresses into its later stages (M26-M72), the key messages will evolve to reflect the advancements and outcomes of the research. The next phase will concentrate on fostering deeper engagement, translating research findings into practical applications, and ensuring long-term impact. GlycanTrigger will build on its previous work by offering stakeholders actionable insights, showcasing how the research can be applied in real-world settings, and highlighting the importance of continued collaboration for future success.

Key Messages (M25-M72)

- **Engagement with Patient and Healthcare Communities** – Encourage active participation from patients, patient organisations, healthcare providers, and researchers to help shape the future of IBD treatment and prevention, creating a collaborative and inclusive environment.
- **Translating Research into Action** – Communicate the transition from research findings to practical applications, highlighting the development of new treatments, prevention methods, and potential collaborations with stakeholders such as healthcare professionals, patients, and policymakers.
- **Engagement and Impact** – Emphasise the importance of continued stakeholder involvement, community engagement, and collaboration to ensure the successful implementation and dissemination of GlycanTrigger's solutions.
- **What's Next for GlycanTrigger** – Set expectations for the next phases of the project, focusing on scaling up research and developing concrete.

Effective communication ensures that the right messages reach the right audiences at the right time, using appropriate formats. Defining stakeholders and their interests is essential to achieving the project's objectives, and the selection of dissemination tools and target groups is crucial.

2.2 Dissemination Strategy

With key dissemination channels and tools already implemented, the GlycanTrigger dissemination strategy has entered a phase of maximising reach and engagement. This phase aims to sustain impact while fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among project stakeholders. By strategically using established dissemination channels and tools, the project ensures that stakeholders can readily access project research and outcomes, and gain a deeper understanding of IBD.

The updated GlycanTrigger dissemination strategy focuses on four main objectives:

- **Expanding Reach:** Make project findings accessible to a wide range of sectors, including the medical community, scientific researchers, and the general public, with a focus on tools for personalised IBD prevention and early diagnosis.
- **Promoting Adoption:** It aims to facilitate the uptake of findings by healthcare providers, industry, and policymakers, especially in transforming prevention measures and treatments for IBD.
- **Encouraging Collaboration:** By fostering connections with EU-funded projects and international research initiatives, GlycanTrigger ensures knowledge exchange and greater collaboration within the IBD research community.
- **Sustaining Impact Beyond the Project Lifecycle:** Leverages established channels to keep stakeholders, including Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), patient groups, and the media, engaged and informed, ensuring the continued impact of GlycanTrigger's findings.

These objectives ensure the project's research is widely disseminated and remains influential across various sectors. Each dissemination tool continues to serve specific stakeholder groups as outlined in Table 2.

Table 2 - Groups targeted by each dissemination channel and tool

	Target Groups							
	Medical and healthcare community	Scientific and technology community	Policymakers	Industry	NGOs and medical associations	Patients & their families	Civil Society	Media
Website	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Social media	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Scientific publications	x	x	x	x	x			x
Thematic webinars and workshops	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Training	x				x	x		
Internal and external events	x	x	x	x	x			
Newsletter	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

2.3 Potential risks and mitigation measures

To sustain the effectiveness of communication and dissemination efforts, GlycanTrigger proactively monitors potential risks and implements measures to address challenges that may arise. Table 3 highlights these risks and the corresponding mitigation strategies, which are continuously refined based on ongoing project activities and feedback from stakeholders.

Table 3 - Potential Risks and Mitigation Measures

Risk for implementation	Level	Mitigation Measure
Contributions from partners (e.g., website, social media and newsletters)	Low	Increase the direct contacts with WP leaders to identify inside each WP interesting materials to disseminate, able to catch the attention of target public
Levels of interaction with website and social media	Medium	More active collaboration of partners could be requested to disseminate the project within their networks
Low engagement from external stakeholders (e.g., industry, policymakers, patients)	Medium	Organise targeted webinars, workshops, and roundtable discussions to foster direct engagement. Tailor content to the specific needs and interests of stakeholders
Limited public awareness of IBD and their significance	Medium	Focus on public awareness campaigns through social media, newsletters, and collaboration with patient associations to promote health literacy on IBD

Chapter 3

Communication and Dissemination Activities

3. Communication and Dissemination Activities

This section describes the tools, channels, and activities executed for the external communication in order to guarantee that the GlycanTrigger messages, progresses, and achievements are disseminated effectively to the target audiences. Besides the creation and maintenance of the communication channels, GlycanTrigger also intends to leverage the partners' networks to increase the project's reach. Detailed descriptions of existing channels are provided in the subsequent sections.

3.1 Visual Identity

The visual identity of GlycanTrigger was established in the beginning of the project in order to make it easily identifiable and to standardise the visual elements. As the project progressed, new materials were developed to meet the evolving needs of the consortium. The visual identity includes:

- Visual identity elements for website and social media
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for deliverables
- Template for agenda events
- Poster template for project presentations at events.
- Brand manual, including the logo variations, colour palette, fonts, and visibility of EU funding

3.2 Website

Glycantrigger's website (www.glycantrigger.eu) was designed to collect all the outcomes of the project and serve as the main repository for its research, communication and dissemination efforts (Figure 1). Launched in April 2023 (M4), the website is regularly updated by SPI, and provides comprehensive information about the project, including its objects, research outputs, media materials, and relevant news. The website is structured as follows:

- **Homepage:** introduces the project, emphasising its focus on understanding the role of glycans in IBD, along with the latest highlights and news, consortium partners list, contact information, and an option to subscribe to the project's newsletter;
- **About:** provides an overview of the project, including its scope, objectives, workplan, expected impact, details about the consortium partners, and information about the projects funded under the same call ("Personalised Blueprint of Chronic inflammation in health-to-disease transition" (HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-02-01)), referred "sister projects".
- **Our Research:** serves as a repository for various project-related resources, including public deliverables, scientific publications, and useful links.

- **Societal Impact (new tab):** this section covers the activities and outputs related to patient empowerment and health literacy, including records of the GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium. It is designed to support patients seeking more information about IBDs and their clinical management, as well as to inform healthcare professionals about the latest developments in these areas.
- **Media:** includes various media materials, including the GlycanTrigger promotional video, GlycanTrigger podcast series, press releases, and the project brochure and roll-up.
- **News & Events:** features News & Events and Newsletter sub-sections, providing an organised platform for staying updated on the latest developments and activities within the GlycanTrigger project.
- **Contacts:** Redirects the webpage visitors to the main contacts of the project.

Figure 1 – Homepage of GlycanTrigger Website

The website currently has 1,143 visitors and 4,374 page views, with an average of engagement time of 1 minute and 22 seconds. According to Google Analytics, the majority of visitors come from Portugal, the United States, Germany, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. The traffic analysis helps assess how visitors are discovering the website, using the following parameters: i) referral/mention traffic indicates the success of collaborations and external features; ii) organic social traffic measures the impact of social media campaigns; iii) organic search traffic reflects the project visibility on the search engines, and by iv) direct search traffic it shows how many users are actively seeking out the GlycanTrigger website by entering the URL directly. The major sources of access to the website are through direct search (638 visitors) and organic search (311), followed by organic social (121 visitors) and referral (73). This data allows for continuous optimization of communication and dissemination strategies, enabling the consortium to focus on effective media channels and strengthen the visibility and accessibility of key messages.

3.3 Social media

Social media has gained significant importance in today's world, in a way that is almost obligatory to harness its potential in terms of outreach. Therefore, GlycanTrigger uses three social media channels to share project updates and disseminate outputs (Figure 2).

- **LinkedIn:** <https://www.linkedin.com/company/glycantrigger-eu-project/>
- **X:** <https://x.com/GlycanTrigger>
- **Instagram:** https://www.instagram.com/glycantrigger_project/

Figure 2 - GlycanTrigger's social media platforms: LinkedIn (top left), X (right), and Instagram (bottom left)

From March 2023 to November 2024, GlycanTrigger has posted 248 publications across these platforms, gaining 584 followers on LinkedIn, 187 followers on X, and 166 followers on Instagram. Each platform allows for refined content that suits the preferences and behaviours of its user base. LinkedIn is ideal for professional engagement and for the share of publications, X for real-time updates, and Instagram for real-time dissemination (through stories) and for visually appealing content that captures the project's essence and engages a broader and more dynamic audience. All social media platforms are managed by the SPI.

These channels allow GlycanTrigger to target multiple target audiences, including researchers, healthcare professionals, industry, policymakers, and the general public. **Regular updates keep the stakeholders informed about the project progress and achievements** (Figure 3). Real-time dissemination ensures that the audience stays engaged and aware of the key milestones and developments of the project. The regularity and well-curated posts contribute to the development of a project's online presence and ensure the consistent communication with its audience.

The GlycanTrigger actively engages its audience through regular updates on the project news, job opportunities, partner awards, as well as by the participation in external events. These communication efforts display an essential role at boosting the visibility of the project and ensures that key stakeholders, including researchers, industry professionals, and the general public, are informed and engaged with the latest developments.

Figure 3 – Examples of posts created for GlycanTrigger's social media channels to communicate and disseminate project activities

In addition to updates about the latest project developments (Figure 4), the project's social media channels also play an instrumental role in promoting **health literacy**. The project developed a social media campaign titled **“Understanding IBD: Bridging Knowledge Towards Disease Prediction and Prevention”**. This monthly series provides accurate, accessible information about IBD, covering topics such as causes, symptoms, diagnosis, treatment, self-advocacy, and mental health (Table 4). The campaign, which began in September 2023, aims to educate and empower individuals affected by IBD and foster community engagement. Scheduled to run until April 2025, the campaign's content will culminate in an IBD health literacy book, adapted from the series. This resource will be made available on the project's website until the end of 2025, ensuring lasting access to valuable information.

Table 4 – Overview of Publications for "Understanding IBD: Bridging Knowledge Towards Disease Prediction and Prevention" campaign

Publication Date	Publication Topic
September 2023	Inflammatory Bowel Disease
October 2023	Facts about Crohn's Disease
November 2023	Facts about Ulcerative Colitis
December 2023	Differences between Remission and Relapse
January 2024	Causes of Inflammatory Bowel Disease
February 2024	Symptoms of Inflammatory Bowel Disease
March 2024	Comparing Symptoms: Crohn's Disease vs. Ulcerative Colitis
April 2024	Types of Crohn's Disease
June 2024	Diagnostic Process for Inflammatory Bowel Disease
July 2024	Treatment and Care Options of Inflammatory Bowel Disease
August 2024	Preclinical phase of Inflammatory Bowel Disease
September 2024	Economic Impact of Inflammatory Bowel Disease
October 2024	Mental Health Impact of Inflammatory Bowel Disease
November 2024	Prevention of Inflammatory Bowel Disease

Figure 4 – Examples of posts created for the campaign "Understanding IBD: Bridging Knowledge Towards Disease Prediction and Prevention"

The project also celebrates key **commemorative days** that align with its mission (Table 5), such as **World IBD Day** to raise awareness of IBDs and **World Health Day**, which promotes global health equity.

Additionally, the project supports initiatives that champion gender equality, including the **International Day of Women and Girls in Science**, which encourages gender equality in STEM and highlights women's contributions to health research, as well as **International Women's Day**, which recognises the social, economic, cultural, and political achievements of women. These events provide an opportunity to amplify the project's message and engage with a wider audience. Moreover, some of these campaigns were conducted in collaboration with other sister projects, fostering the collaboration within EU-funded projects.

Table 5 - Calendar of the GlycanTrigger's Commemorative days (May 2023 – November 2024)

2023	
May	
19	World IBD Day
June	
27	World Microbiome Day
December	
1-7	World Crohn's and Colitis Awareness Week
2024	
February	
11	International Day of Women and Girls in Science
March	
8	Woman Day
April	
7	World Health Day
May	
9	Europe Day
29	World Digestive Health Day
June	
27	World Microbiome Day
October	
10	Mental Health Day

Figure 5 – Examples of posts created for the GlycanTrigger's Commemorative days

Through regular posts and social media campaigns, GlycanTrigger reinforces its visibility within the Horizon Europe community and beyond. These efforts foster dialogue with other HE projects, researchers, and healthcare stakeholders, creating opportunities for collaboration and enhancing the likelihood of synergy with other projects and institutions.

3.4 Press releases

A press release is a critical component of the project communication activities. It displays an effective tool for the dissemination of key information about the project to a broad audience, including media outlets, stakeholders, and the general public. The second GlycanTrigger press release (Figure 6), launched on October 17th, announced the presence of GlycanTrigger at the European Researchers' Night 2024 event, an initiative funded by the European Commission under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. The document was published in English and disseminated through GlycanTrigger's social media and website (<https://glycantrigger.eu/media/#press>). This type of actions increases the visibility of the GlycanTrigger project, particularly within the framework of HE initiatives. It informs external audiences—such as researchers, policymakers, industry partners, and patients—about the project's objectives, the challenges it addresses, and the potential impact on areas such as IBDs treatment and research.

GLYCANTRIGGER PARTICIPATES IN EUROPEAN RESEARCHERS' NIGHT 2024

Porto, Portugal - September 27th, 2024

The GlycanTrigger project, funded by Horizon Europe, participated in the European Researchers' Night 2024, held at i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde. This annual event, celebrated across Europe, aims to bridge the gap between science and the general public.

The GlycanTrigger project showcased its research on the role of glycans in gut health and their involvement in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). The team conducted interactive demonstrations, including the opportunity to observe histological slides of intestinal tissue through a microscope. These activities helped explain how changes in mucosa glycome can trigger inflammation and potentially lead to new therapeutic approaches for IBD.

"The European Researchers' Night provides a great platform for us to communicate the importance of glycans in health and disease to the general public and to the society" said Carolina Dantas, PhD student of the GlycanTrigger project. "We are excited to share our progress and engage directly with the community".

GlycanSwitch, another major study within the Immunology, Cancer and Glycomedicine group at i3S and funded by an ERC Synergy Grant, was also featured at the event. This project explores autoimmune diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, focusing on the critical role of protein glycosylation in immune regulation.

"The European Researchers' Night provides a great platform for us to communicate the importance of glycans in health and disease to the general public and to the society"

Both projects engaged visitors through hands-on activities, including educational games designed to highlight the importance of protein glycosylation in health and disease, attracting participants of all ages.

For more information on the GlycanTrigger project, visit www.glycantrigger.eu

Information on the GlycanSwitch project can be found here: www.glycanswitch.com

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Figure 6 - GlycanTrigger second press release

3.5 Visual Communication Materials

Visual communication materials, including a project brochure and roll-up banner, were developed to convey the project's objectives, and expected outcomes to the target audience in a clear and accessible way (Figure 7). These materials have been widely distributed in third parties events and are also available for download on the project website. Additional materials will be developed throughout the project and included in future updates of this plan.

Figure 7 - GlycanTrigger trifold brochure (left) and roll-up banner (right)

3.6 E-newsletter

The regular publication of a newsletter displays a crucial role at providing an effective communication with a broad collection of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, industry partners, and the general public. GlycanTrigger’s newsletter offers subscribers regular updates on the most recent project activities, the latest scientific publications, and upcoming events (Table 6). All the editions are accessible on the project website (<https://glycantrigger.eu/news-events/newsletter/>), and distributed via email to the subscribers. Two newsletters per year are planned until the project’s conclusion, with the next issue scheduled for release in December 2024.

Table 6 – GlycanTrigger Newsletter editions and subscribers

Issue	Release Date	Content	No. of Subscribers
<u>Newsletter 1</u>	June 2023	Inaugural issue: Introduction to the GlycanTrigger project, kick-off meeting, scientific publications, news, and upcoming events	29
<u>Newsletter 2</u>	November 2023	Reflections on the first year of GlycanTrigger, launch of the project promotional video, project meetings and events, awards, scientific publications, synergies with sister projects	59
<u>Newsletter 3</u>	May 2024	Launch of the GlycanTrigger Podcast Series, project meetings, media outreach, upcoming events and activities, project campaigns, synergies with sister projects	75

In addition, the partner EFCCA launched a newsletter in August 2023, titled “**EFCCA Project Digest**”, to keep its network informed on the latest developments in the HE projects in which EFCCA is involved. GlycanTrigger has been featured in all four issues released to date:

- [Issue #1](#) (August 2023)
- [Issue #2](#) (November 2023)
- [Issue #3](#) (February 2024)
- [Issue #4](#) (June 2024)
- [Issue #5](#) (November 2024)

3.7 Podcast/Videos

Audio and audio-visual materials have been developed as dynamic tools for the engagement of several types of target audiences and enhancing the dissemination of the project's objectives and results. These materials are available across multiple project channels, including the project website, social media platforms, [YouTube channel](#) (@glycantrigger), and [GlycanTrigger Spotify channel](#).

The **GlycanTrigger Podcast Series**, launched in January 2024, aims to facilitate short discussions (around 30 minutes per episode) on topics such as IBD, lifestyle management, and patient empowerment (Figure 8). It engages with IBD experts, patients, and other specialists, exploring their work and challenges.

Figure 8 - Profile pages of GlycanTrigger YouTube (left) and Spotify (right) channels

Guests include members of the GlycanTrigger consortium and partners from other sister EU-funded projects. To date, two episodes have been released and are available on YouTube (videocast version), Spotify (audio version) as well as the project website and social media channels. About ten more episodes are planned for release during the lifespan of GlycanTrigger (Table 7).

Table 7 - List of GlycanTrigger Podcast Series Episodes

Episode	Episode Title	Moderator/ Guests	Release Date	No. of Listeners
1	Where are we and to where we want to go in IBD prediction and Prevention	Moderator: Salomé Pinho (i3s) Guests: Joana Torres (Hospital da Luz), Luisa Avedano (EFCCA)	18/01/2024	146
2	How gut permeability impacts inflammatory and autoimmune diseases	Moderator: Leticia Gomes (i3s) Guests: Gonçalo Barreto (ENDOTARGET), Patrícia Costa-Reis (ENDOTARGET), Salomé Pinho (i3s)	07/10/2024	81

Additionally, a promotional video for the project was created (Figure 9) as a powerful visual tool to engage audiences with GlycanTrigger's mission and highlight the value of its research. Videos are ideal for sharing across social media, websites, and events, providing an engaging and visually compelling format to convey

the project's key messages. By presenting complex information in a digestible, easy-to-understand way, these educational videos can reach a wider audience and generate interest in the project's findings and innovations. The video was showcased during the European Night of Researchers at i3S, where it was presented to civil society, helping to extend its reach and impact. The video has accumulated over 300 views on YouTube. A new video is planned for 2025, summarizing the achievements and activities from the project's first two years.

Figure 9 - GlycanTrigger promotional video

Together, podcasts and educational videos reinforce the dissemination strategy of GlycanTrigger by the amplification of such visibility, engagement, and the knowledge generated by the project. The multimedia approach also supports two-way communication by encouraging feedback and interaction actions with stakeholders, thereby supporting the project's overarching goals of sustainability and long-term impact.

3.8 Scientific Publications and Deliverables

The research conducted in the GlycanTrigger project has led to the production of scientific publications on the role of glycans in the transition from health to inflammation. These outputs facilitate the dissemination of the project's progress and the knowledge generated to the medical and research communities, industry, as well as the general public. To maximise the impact and reach of these publications, these outputs are published in widely accessible, peer-reviewed journals as open resources (Open Access journals) and, whenever possible, on preprint servers (e.g., MedRxiv, BioRxiv) to ensure easy access to research data. This approach allows potentially impactful findings to be rapidly available, accelerating further research and applications in clinical practice. All publications developed within GlycanTrigger are available on the project website. A list of project publications can be found below:

- Vicente, M. M., Alves, I., Fernandes, Â., Dias, A. M., Santos-Pereira, B., Pérez-Anton, E., ... & Pinho, S. S. (2023). *Mannosylated glycans impair normal T-cell development by reprogramming commitment and repertoire diversity*. *Cellular & Molecular Immunology*, 20(8), 955-968. doi: [10.1038/s41423-023-01052-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41423-023-01052-7)
- Vicente, M. M., Leite-Gomes, E., & Pinho, S. S. (2023). *Glycome dynamics in T and B cell development: basic immunological mechanisms and clinical applications*. *Trends in Immunology*, 40 (8), 585-597. doi:[10.1016/j.it.2023.06.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.it.2023.06.004)
- Pinho, S. S., Alves, I., Gaifem, J., & Rabinovich, G. A. (2023). *Immune regulatory networks coordinated by glycans and glycan-binding proteins in autoimmunity and infection*. *Cellular & Molecular Immunology*, 20(10), 1101-1113. doi: [10.1038/s41423-023-01074-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41423-023-01074-1)
- Gaifem J, Rodrigues CS, Petralia F, Alves I, Leite-Gomes E, Cavadas B, Dias AM, Moreira-Barbosa C, Revés J, Laird RM, Novokmet M, Štambuk J, Habazin S, Turhan B, Gümüő ZH, Ungaro R, Torres J, Lauc G, Colombel JF, Porter CK, Pinho SS. (2024). *A unique serum IgG glycosylation signature predicts development of Crohn's disease and is associated with pathogenic antibodies to mannose glycan*. *Nature Immunology*, 25(9):1692-1703. doi: [10.1038/s41590-024-01916-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41590-024-01916-8)
- Almeida P, Fernandes Â, Alves I, Pinho SS. (2024). *Glycans in Trained Immunity: Educators of innate immune memory in homeostasis and disease*. *Carbohydrate Research*, 544:109245.
- Crouch LI, Rodrigues CS, Bakshani CR, Tavares-Gomes L, Gaifem J, Pinho SS. (2024). *The role of glycans in health and disease: Regulators of the interaction between gut microbiota and host immune system*. *Seminars in Immunology*, 9(73):101891. doi: [10.1016/j.smim.2024.101891](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smim.2024.101891)

Moreover, the project deliverables with a dissemination level “Public” and approved by the European Commission are also available on the project website. These deliverables are outlined in the project’s Grant Agreement (GA) and are essential for tracking the project’s advancement and ensuring compliance with EU funding requirements. They represent the tangible outcomes of the project, documenting its results, methodologies, and impacts. The list of available deliverables is presented below and can also be found on the project website.

- D1.1 Definition of the gut glycome map along health to inflammation transition.
- D5.1 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 1
- D5.6 Project website
- D6.1 Risk assessment analysis
- D6.2 Development and update of the Data Management Plan 1

3.9 Events

The GlycanTrigger consortium is actively hosting and participating in several events aimed at communicating the project outcomes, engaging with several of the target groups, and exploring opportunities for collaboration (e.g. with sister projects). These events include two main types:

- **Internal events:** These are being organised by GlycanTrigger partners to (1) facilitate communication and collaboration among the consortium, and (2) engage relevant stakeholders and researchers to boost collaboration and involvement in the project's key initiatives. which include the project kick-off meeting (March 2023) and the project Steering Committee and General Assembly meetings (September 2023, April 2024, October 2024), provide a platform for partners to share progress, discuss challenges, and strategize on future activities, ensuring that all consortium members are aligned and working toward common goals.

Upcoming internal events include the GlycanTrigger General Assembly in May 2025, hosted in Paris, France (Sorbonne University), with all nine partners and team members. The annual Steering Committee meeting and External Advisory Board (EAB) meeting will take place online in September 2025, bringing together WP leaders and EAB members.

- **External events:** GlycanTrigger partners are also participating in conferences, symposiums, and events organised by external entities. Participation in these events aims to improve the dissemination of the project's findings and promote its innovative research to a broader audience, including policymakers, the scientific community, and potential users of GlycanTrigger's research outcomes. The list of events attended by GlycanTrigger partners is presented in Table 8.

Table 8 – List of events attended by GlycanTrigger partners in 2023 and 2024

Partner	Event	Date	Location	Target Audience
i3s	3rd International GlycoBioTec Symposium 2023	17-19 Jan, 2023	Berlin, Germany	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community
i3s	Spanish Carbohydrate Meeting 2023	27-29 Mar, 2023	Barcelona, Spain	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community
i3s LMUC	26th International Symposium on Glycoconjugates (Glyco26)	27 Aug, 2023-1 Sept, 2023	Taipei, Taiwan	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community
i3s	Sialoglycan Meeting	9-11 Oct, 2023	Hannover, Germany.	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community

EFCCA GLSMED LH Mount Sinai	United European Gastroenterology Week 2023	14-17 Oct, 2023	Copenhagen, Denmark	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community, Patient's Associations
I3s SPI	2nd Biannual Consortium Meeting of ENDOTARGET	27 Oct, 2023	Santiago Compostela, Spain /Zoom	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community
EFCCA	European Crohn's and Colitis Organisation (ECCO) Congress 2024	21-24 Feb, 2024	Stockholm, Sweden	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community; Patients' Associations
i3s	5th GeneGut General Assembly	6-7 June, 2024	Porto, Portugal	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community
i3s	Glyco-core Symposium 2024	6 Jul, 2024	Aichi, Japan	Scientific & Technological community
I3s Mount Sinai	IBD Retreat Meeting	17 Jun, 2024	New York, USA	Scientific & Technological community; Medical & healthcare community
i3s	7th European Congress of Immunology	1-4 Sep, 2024	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific & Technological community
i3s SPI	European Researchers' Night	27 Sep, 2024	Porto, Portugal	Civil Society
I3s	Human Glycome Project Meeting	23-24, Oct, 2024	Split, Croatia	Scientific & Technological community

A list of the most important public events in Europe concerning IBDs, glycobiology, and healthcare innovation is being considered for GlycanTrigger's participation. Engaging in these events will allow the project to present its objectives and research findings through papers, roll-ups, presentations, and other dissemination materials. In this context, partners plan to potentially participate in the events identified in Table 9, which will provide valuable platforms for knowledge exchange and further strengthen the project's visibility within the scientific community and healthcare sector.

Table 9 – Upcoming events to be attended by GlycanTrigger partners

Event	Description	Date	Location
European Crohn's and Colitis Organisation (ECCO) Congress	Annual event focused on the latest clinical research, treatment approaches, and innovations for IBD	February 2025 (Annual)	Berlin, Germany
GlycoBioTec 2025	International conference on the intersection of glycobiology and biotechnology	February 2025	Berlin, Germany
27th International Symposium on Glycoconjugates (Glyco27)	Symposium featuring the latest advancements in glycobiology and glycoconjugate research	March 2025	Edmonton, Canada
Glycobiology Gordon Research Conference	Research conference focusing on the molecular and functional roles of glycans.	March 2025	Lucca, Italy
United European Gastroenterology (UEG) Week	Event for gastroenterology, covering a wide range of GI and liver diseases, including IBD	October (annual)	Varies across Europe
FEBS Congress 2025	Annual congress featuring discussions on biochemical research, including glycobiology	June 2025	Prague, Czech Republic

3.9.1 1st GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium

As part of its ongoing commitment to enhancing knowledge and fostering collaboration, the GlycanTrigger project places significant emphasis on events focused on health literacy, patient empowerment, and self-management (e.g. webinars, co-creation workshops). These activities are designed to bridge the gap between research advancements and practical applications, ensuring that the project's findings are translated into actionable knowledge that benefits all stakeholders.

The 1st GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium was held virtually via Zoom on November 19th, 2024 (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Organized by SPI and EFCCA, the event brought together experts, patients, and healthcare professionals to foster collaboration and advance understanding of IBD. The symposium covered key topics including IBD risk factors, prevention strategies, and the essential role of patient empowerment in managing the condition.

The symposium agenda included a webinar session focused on identifying risk factors, prevention measures, and patient counselling strategies, presented by Dr. Joana Revés (Gastroenterologist, Hospital Beatriz Ângelo). This was followed by a co-creation workshop that explored the role of patient engagement in managing IBD. During this session, invited speakers discussed the impact of nutrition, stress, and overall health management on the progression of IBD, and shared their perspectives on IBD treatment as patients. Speakers included Professor Guendalina Graffigna (miGut-Health project), as well as Cândida Cruz and

Filipa Cunha from the Portuguese IBD Patient Association (APDI). The final session featured a workshop on health literacy in IBD management, with contributions from Dr. Joana Torres (Gastroenterologist, Hospital da Luz Learning Health) and two patients from the EFCCA Youth Group, who shared their professional and personal perspectives on health literacy in managing IBD. All sessions encouraged participant interaction through Zoom's Q&A feature and Slido, an application used for live polling and question submissions.

The event attracted 74 registrations from 18 countries, with 41 active participants joining the online session. These included two clinicians, eight IBD patient representatives, seven IBD patients, 18 researchers, and six individuals categorized as “other”. The symposium was also streamed live on [YouTube](#), where it has already garnered over 95 views. These figures highlight the success of the inaugural GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium, which provided valuable insights and stimulated thoughtful discussions. With a duration of 2 hours, the symposium served as a vital platform for sharing knowledge, strengthening the link between research and patient care, and fostering dialogue within the IBD community.

A second edition of the GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium is scheduled for autumn 2025. This will be an in-person event, continuing the success of the first symposium and providing further opportunities for engagement within the IBD community.

Figure 10 – 1st GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium: Event dissemination poster (top left), Agenda (top right), and Zoom session capture (bottom)

3.10 Media

The groundbreaking research of the GlycanTrigger project was also featured in the Portuguese media. The magazine *Visão Saúde* published an article titled *"The War Within Us" (A guerra dentro de nós)* (Figure 11). The article highlighted significant advancements in understanding conditions associated with chronic inflammation, such as IBD.

The project gained further visibility through features in prominent Portuguese outlets, including SIC Notícias and Público. *SIC Notícias* highlighted the discovery of a blood alteration that could predict the onset of Crohn's disease, shedding light on the project's potential to transform early detection and intervention strategies. Similarly, *Público* focused on i3S's leadership in advancing early intervention strategies for Crohn's disease through GlycanTrigger's innovative research. These media highlights underscore the significant impact of GlycanTrigger's research in advancing our understanding and treatment of autoimmune diseases.

Figure 11 – GlycanTrigger project featured in Portuguese media

3.11 Synergies

GlycanTrigger has established synergies with its sister projects – EU projects funded by the call topic “Personalised Blueprint of Chronic inflammation in health-to-disease transition” (HORIZON-HLTH-2022-STAYHLTH-02-01). These projects share the common goal of understanding the risk factors that trigger the transition from health to disease, providing personalised prevention measures and reducing the burden of chronic diseases. Since M9, WP5 has been in regular contact with the dissemination and communication team leaders of [ENDOTARGET](#), [miGUT-Health](#), [IMMEDIATE](#) and [iPROLEPSIS](#) to coordinate efforts, enhance project visibility, and facilitate knowledge exchange among researchers in order to achieve the expected outcomes of the call.

Joint initiatives have included social media campaigns on shared themes. For instance, on International Women's Day, GlycanTrigger and ENDOTARGET launched a collaborative campaign emphasising gender balance within their teams and reaffirming a commitment to gender equality in European research (Figure 12 top right). A subsequent collaborative campaign for Europe Day brought together all sister projects to celebrate unity in diversity, innovation, and cross-continental collaboration (Figure 12 top left). Beyond social media, GlycanTrigger utilised its Podcast Series as a platform for promoting discussions and sharing insights with researchers from other projects (Figure 12 bottom). Additionally, a dedicated section in the GlycanTrigger newsletter highlights sister project developments, including upcoming events, workshops, and collaborative activities, further strengthening cross-project visibility and interaction.

Looking ahead, in January 2025, GlycanTrigger will participate in a series of meetings with sister projects to coordinate a cluster-wide scientific collaboration. These efforts include plans for joint initiatives such as a symposium or conference later in 2025 to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange.

Figure 12 – GlycanTrigger’s collaborations with its sister project, ENDOTARGET: joint campaign with ENDOTARGET for International Women’s Day (top left); collaborative campaign with all sister projects for Europe Day (top right); GlycanTrigger podcast episode featuring researchers from the ENDOTARGET project as guests (bottom)

Chapter 4

Monitoring

4. Monitoring

The primary goal of monitoring is to make sure that the communication plan is well executed. Regular monitoring of the project's communication and dissemination activities is essential for assessing their impact, which is crucial for the successful implementation of the GlycanTrigger project. Ongoing monitoring will help evaluate the quality of communication efforts, identify areas for improvement, and determine if any updates or adjustments are needed to achieve the project's goals. This evaluation process will be continuous and will be broken down into three key components: Monitoring can be broken down into sub-sections:

- Performance measurement
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
- Reporting

4.1 Performance Measurement

The performance measurement focuses on assessing the results and effectiveness of the ongoing communication and dissemination activities. It evaluates how well the project's messages and objectives have been received and understood through the level of engagement with the GlycanTrigger project among stakeholders and the target audience. Regular monitoring of project visibility, stakeholder engagement, and message effectiveness is regularly conducted to ensure that the project's strategy remains aligned with project goals and can be adjusted when necessary. Data is collected and analysed by SPI and shared with all project partners every 6 months during the consortium internal meetings.

4.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs enable the quantitative assessment of performance by setting target values for communication goals. Table 10 presents KPIs for GlycanTrigger communication and dissemination activities, the means for their verification and respective metrics achieved. These KPIs will continue to be monitored to guide decision-making and ensure continuous improvement.

Table 10 - KPIs of GlycanTrigger communication strategy and respective metrics

Tools & Channels	KPIs	Means of verification	Metrics
Website	No. of visitors per year: 1700 visitors with at least 2 minutes/visit	Google Analytics	1016 visitors 1,1 minutes/visit (Nov 2023 – Nov 2024)
Social Media	Total no. of followers and no. of posts per year: 1,000 followers (total) and 15 posts/year	Social media analytics	937 followers (total) >100 posts/year
Press releases	No. of press releases: At least 2 press releases/year	Project reporting, website analytics	1 press release/year 2 press releases (total)

Visual communication materials	No. of infographics developed and no. of downloads: 800 printed brochures/flyers and 500 downloads	Website analytics	> 800 printed materials (brochure and roll up) 27 downloads
E-newsletter	No. of newsletters and no. of subscribers: 3 newsletters per year and at least 250 subscribers	Platform analytics	2 newsletter per year (3 newsletters in total) 78 subscribers
Podcast	No. of podcast listeners: At least 80 listeners/podcast episode	Platform analytics	80 listeners/podcast episode 227 listeners (total)
Videos	No. of videos produced and no. of views: 3 videos and at least 150 views/video/year.	Platform analytics	1 video 347 views

Regarding the project's events, Table 11 outlines the KPIs for event-related activities as specified in the project's Grant Agreement.

Table 11 - KPIs of GlycanTrigger event-related activities and respective metrics

Event	Description	KPIs	Metrics
Opening Event	Kick-off meeting	At least 50 participants	45 participants
Third Party Events	Dissemination through lectures, conferences, and interviews; participation in ECCO/UEG Congresses, Glycobiology congresses, and EFCCA General Assembly.	N/A	13 events (Table 8)
Health Literacy	GlycanTrigger Research Webinar Series: Biannual webinars on chronic disease risk factors and prevention.	15 participants	41 participants
	GlycanTrigger Joint Workshop Series: Biannual workshops with EU projects on patient empowerment guidelines.	10 participants	
Patient Empowerment and Self-Management	GlycanTrigger Online Co-creation Workshops: Yearly patient-centred events for input on chronic diseases and self-management tools.	10 participants	41 participants

The Health Literacy and Patient Empowerment and Self-Management events were held during the 1st GlycanTrigger Patients Symposium. This event included webinars on chronic disease prevention, joint workshops with EU project (miGut-Health project) on patient empowerment, and co-creation workshops on self-management tools, engaging a total of 41 participants (see section 3.9.1).

4.3 Reporting

For communication and dissemination activities, all partners are required to inform SPI about their participation in or organisation of any dissemination events. The outcomes of these activities are reported to the partners during the biannual consortium meetings, which provide an opportunity to review results and adjust strategies as needed. To facilitate this process, SPI has developed and manages dedicated reporting templates. Every six months, SPI sends an email to the consortium mailing list, requesting partners to provide updates on relevant news, scientific publications, participation in events, and information about any upcoming events in which they intend to participate.

Chapter 5

GlycanTrigger Exploitation Strategy

5. GlycanTrigger Exploitation Strategy

The exploitation strategy is positioned at developing a sustainable exit plan to efficiently exploit tangible and intangible project results towards maximising impact. Exploitation efforts began early in the project and will extend beyond project lifetime. Developed under Task 5.1 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan”, the strategy is designed to ensure the take up of GlycanTrigger’s results for commercial, research, and medical purposes. Overall, the Exploitation Strategy will ensure that non-confidential knowledge and results are shared with proper audiences and stakeholders.

5.1 Exploitation Objectives

The main objectives of the exploitation plan of GlycanTrigger are:

- To effectively **deliver the relevant knowledge, outcomes and results produced to the target groups** identified;
- To **deliver a measurable benefit to society** through the **valorisation of project outcomes** and its **Key Exploitable Results (KERs)**;
- To contribute to the project’s sustainability in terms of **knowledge transfer** and **replicability beyond the funding period**.

A methodology for the Exploitation Strategy has been developed to ensure the successful exploitation of GlycanTrigger project’s results and their long impact. This methodology is structured into three phases: **Preparation, Implementation, and Post-Project**. Each phase builds upon the last to maximise the project’s outcomes, as outlined in Table 12.

Table 12 - Phases of GlycanTrigger Exploitation Strategy.

Phase	Goals	Key Actions
Preparation Phase (M1-M24)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish the foundation for exploitation. - Identify KERs and target stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop a comprehensive exploitation strategy. - Identify KERs. - Map stakeholders (industry, healthcare, policymakers, etc.). - Start disseminating non-confidential results. - Set up communication and dissemination channels.

Implementation Phase (M24-M60)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actively pursue exploitation efforts. - Convert results into tangible benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage with industry for technological/commercial exploitation. - Foster joint R&D collaborations and open-access publications. - Empower the medical community through workshops and guidelines. - Track impact using Key Impact Pathways (KIPs). - Manage Intellectual Property (IP).
Post-Project Phase (M60-M72)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure long-term sustainability and impact. - Secure the exploitation of results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use the Horizon Results Platform (Horizon Results Booster) to license or transfer results. - Advocate for policy integration and societal impact. - Continue engagement with stakeholders to maximise impact. - Finalise IP management and ownership agreements.

5.2 Key impact pathways (KIPs)

To monitor and increase the impact of EU-funded projects, HE relies on the concept of Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) (Table 13) to maximise the insight of stakeholders regarding the benefits and effects of the funded projects in the economy and society. The KIPs consist of storylines that can be used to effectively communicate the project. Identifying KIPs will allow the selection of time-sensitive indicators (short, medium and long-term) to support the monitorization of the project's impact. Such indicators are proposed for each KIP and can be re(de)finned for the specific purposes of the project.

Table 13 - Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) in Horizon Europe

Category	Key Impact Pathway
Scientific impact	KIP1. Creating high-quality new knowledge KIP2. Strengthening human capital in research and innovation KIP3. Fostering diffusion of knowledge and Open Source
Societal impact	KIP4. Addressing EU policy priorities and global challenges through research and innovation KIP5. Delivering benefits and impact through research and innovation missions KIP6. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society
Towards technological/economic impact	KIP7. Generating innovation-based growth KIP8. Creating more and better jobs KIP9. Leveraging investment in research and innovation

Based on GlycanTrigger expected impacts, 6 main KPIs across the three categories are anticipated to be the most relevant pathways to maximise impact and communicate the value of the project:

- **Scientific impact:** Uptake of new open knowledge on the role of glycans in health-to-inflammation transition and in disease prevention will foster novel research and therapies – **KIP1, KIP3**
- **Societal impact:** Patients are empowered and better informed to be able to understand their illness and self-manage their health – **KIP4, KIP5, KIP6**
- **Economic impact:** Reduced burden of chronic inflammatory diseases worldwide that goes far beyond CD and IBD to many other immune mediated disorders (such as diabetes, systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, multiple sclerosis, cardiovascular diseases, among many others) – **KIP7**

5.3 Key Exploitable Results

In HE, a result is defined as *“any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights”*¹.

KERs are selected from a list of expected exploitable results (EERs) by evaluating their innovation, potential for exploitation, and impact. Collaborative efforts from both consortium partners and external stakeholders (such as the external Advisory Board and other relevant parties) are crucial in the development of KERs that have robust value propositions and are closely aligned with societal and commercial demands. One approach to determine and select KERs is involve conducting surveys or workshops to gather the following details for each EER:

1. What are the areas of impact or main target sectors?
2. Which problem will the project outcome solve?
3. Main project results that will be used?
4. Where will the outputs be made available during and after the project?
5. Who are the main end-users of your results?
6. How will you contact them?

The main expected results of GlycanTrigger, as foreseen in the GA are presented in Table 14.

¹ <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/HEU%20Results%20platform.pdf>

Table 14 - Identification of GlycanTrigger expected results

KER	Type of exploitation	WP	Target Group
One new factor underlying health-to-disease transition	Research & Medical	WP1-3	Medical and HCC; Scientific and technology community
One new biomarker as a non-invasive predictive tool	Research & Medical	WP3	Medical and HCC; Scientific and technology community
One new dietary supplement for CD prevention – new product tested in clinical study	Commercial	WP4	Industry
Guidelines for patient empowerment	Medical	WP5	Medical and HCC; Policymakers; Medical associations and NGOs, patients and their families; Civil Society
Culture of dialogue with civil society to empower patients/families about how to deal/prevent IBD	Medical	WP5	Medical and HCC; Policymakers; Medical associations and NGOs; patients and their families; Civil Society; Media

The collection of this information facilitates the creation of a list of KERs and the identification of potential routes for exploitation in relevant impact areas or target sectors. To support the development of KERs work packages with stronger scientific and technological components (WP1-WP4) will play a crucial role by providing the knowledge foundation and the development of potential KERs. For each KER, an exploitation roadmap should be developed, outlining milestones, timelines, and the responsibilities of different partners for effective exploitation. Additionally, for KERs with a high level of technological readiness (TRL), business plans, Go-to-Market (G2M) strategies, or value proposition models should be developed. The Project Management team should be kept informed of and involved in all activities related to the exploitation strategy. Furthermore, strong engagement with stakeholders is critical to understanding market needs and ensuring that KERs have an impact on potential end-users.

KERs can have different forms, including scientific publications, diagnostic tools, training materials, patents, and policy recommendations. Each result should be matched with the relevant target audience, impact area, and intended benefit.

As part of the project's exploitation efforts, a patent request has already been submitted for "Serum glycome-ASCA hub as an early detection biomarker for Crohn's Disease" (Patent_ PPP20232004947082), a promising tool for the early detection of CD, which could facilitate earlier intervention and more effective management of the disease. This patent represents a critical step in protecting the intellectual property associated with one of the project's Key Exploitable Results and underscores its potential for commercial and medical application.

The exploitation strategy encompasses three primary areas - **Technological/Commercial Exploitation**, **Research Exploitation**, and **Medical Exploitation** with several envisioned actions for exploitation (Table 15).

Table 15 - GlycanTrigger exploitation actions

Technological/Commercial Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement with industry to foster the exploitation project results towards • Hosting of GlycanTrigger Transferability Workshop: targeting the medical and healthcare community, policymakers, industry and civil society, for dissemination of self-management tools and exploitable results.
Research Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of joint R&D collaboration opportunities; • Development of links and synergies with other relevant projects; • Open Access Scientific publications and conference presentations.
Medical Exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting collaboration and co-creation with other initiatives and relevant stakeholders, including health care professionals and key opinion leaders; • Establishment of contacts with the medical and healthcare community; • Development of health guidelines and communication with policymakers.

5.4 Potential barriers for exploitation and mitigation strategies

The following barriers to exploitation and mitigation strategies were identified:

1. Limited involvement of patients in the policy-making process

Risk: Limited involvement of patients in policy-making process can result in policies that fail to address their concerns. This can result in lower patient satisfaction, reduced adherence to treatment plans, and decreased trust in the healthcare system. In addition, policies that do not reflect the needs and preferences of patients may not be implemented as intended, leading to decreased effectiveness and wasted resources.

Mitigation Measure: Representatives from patient groups, civil society organisations, and policymakers will be actively involved through a targeted engagement strategy. Collaboration and knowledge-sharing actions will be pursued and patient input will be sought for impact assessment and policy development. GlycanTrigger will also provide and promote access to relevant resources and educational platforms.

2. Lack of citizen's trust and knowledge may limit the adoption of new therapeutic/preventive approaches and healthier choices

Risk: Limited adoption of new treatments and prevention methods can result in poorer health outcomes and increased healthcare costs. In addition, a lack of citizen's trust and knowledge may lead to scepticism and resistance to change, hindering the implementation and scaling up of innovative approaches.

Mitigation Measure: Patients and citizens will be involved throughout the life-cycle of the project; research and clinical developments will be effectively communicated towards fostering access and awareness of the benefits of the proposed approach.

3. Insufficient stakeholder engagement and insufficient awareness

Risk: The stakeholders' feedback may not be incorporated into the research process, resulting in solutions that do not fully meet their needs and expectations. This can lead to a lack of support from stakeholders, hindering the implementation and adoption of new treatments and prevention methods technologies.

Mitigation Measure: Develop specific communication tools to raise awareness and engage all the identified target groups. Actively focus on the lack of input from certain groups, use the multiplier programme and "attract and hold" methodology in online community management to keep stakeholders interested.

5.5 Strategy for Intellectual Property Management

The management of Intellectual Property (IP) is a fundamental factor in the successful exploitation and impact maximisation of the project's results, as well as to the successful and safe implementation of collaborations beyond the project without compromising all partner's best interest and the open science requirements within Horizon Europe projects. Strategies for IP management will be refined according to general EC policies within the scope of **WP6 "Project Management", Task 6.3 "Intellectual property rights"**. Concrete outputs subject to knowledge and IPR management include open-access research publications, datasets, patents, and other knowledge products stemming from GlycanTrigger. IPR will be managed according to principles of the European Commission related to availability of the information, commercial utilisation of results, confidentiality, deliverables, exploitation rights and ownership to third parties and other EU-funded projects following the disclaimer rules. The basic principle underlying herein is that results shall be the property of the partner carrying out the work leading to the results. Where several partners have jointly carried out work generating the results and where their respective share of the work is indivisible, they shall have joint ownership of such results. The partners concerned shall agree in writing the allocation, terms of exercising ownership and protection of the joint results. Distribution within the project should be free of charge, except if it is of confidential commercial nature.

Chapter 6

Final Remarks

6. Final Remarks

The present Deliverable D5.2 - Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan 2, is an update of the Deliverable 5.1 that setup the initial strategy for GlycanTrigger's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, where the guidelines for project partners to enhance the project's impact were provided. Within this deliverable, we refined and expanded the approach set out in D5.1, ensuring that the project's outreach remains relevant and impactful as it progresses. Ongoing monitoring of these activities is essential, and necessary adjustments will be made to the plan through future deliverables, including D5.3 (M48) and D5.4 (M70), to ensure effective engagement with all stakeholders and expand the project's long-term impact.

